

INGLIZ TILINI O'QITISHDA O'QUVCHINI HURMAT QILISH MASALASI

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2 son kasb hunar maktabi ingliz tili fani o'qituvchisi

Annotasiya: Maqolada ingliz tilini o'rgatish, turli metodlardan unumli foydalanish, darsda faol bo'lgan o'quvchilarni baholash va rag'batlantirish masalasi haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Til, javob, baholash, dars, mashq.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются вопросы преподавания английского языка, эффективного использования различных методов, оценки и мотивации учащихся, активных на уроке.

Ключевые слова: Язык, ответ, оценка, урок, упражнение.

Abstract: The article discusses the issue of teaching English, the effective use of various methods, and the assessment and motivation of students who are active in the lesson.

Keywords: Language, response, assessment, lesson, exercise.

Talabalarning g'oyalari unchalik muvaffaqiyatli bo'lmasa-da, o'qituvchi ularni tanqid qilishi mumkin emas. Aksincha, talabalarning ijodiy tafakkuri rag'batlantirib borilishi zarur. Dars tez berilgan javoblarni rag'batlantirish, ularni to'ldirish, talabalarni baholash bilan yakunlanadi.

Savol-javoblar va rasmlı o'yınlar (Discussion) usuli darslarnı yanada mazmunlı va qizıqarlı o'tishga imkon beradi. Talaba xato qilishdan qo'rqmay, erkin

o'z fikrini ayta olishi kerak. Bunday muhit darsda hosil qilinishi lozim. O'yin orqali o'qitishning texnologiyasida talabaning vazifalari quyida gilardan iborat:

1. Kutiladigan javoblar va e'tirozlarni o'ylash.
2. O'z bilimiga ishonish.

O'yinning ahamiyati shundaki, o'qituvchida talabalarni ular erkin holda faoliyat ko'rsatayotgan paytda kuzatish imkoniyati bo'ladi. Natijada talabalarning faolligi, fantaziyalari, ijodiy qobiliyatlari, ishchanliklari, jamoada o'zini tutishlari haqida ko'proq ma'lumotga ega bo'lish mumkin. Talabalar bir nechta guruhlariga bo'linadilar. Guruhlarning har bir a'zosi o'z vazifalarini aniq bilishlari kerak. O'yinning vaqti cheklangan bo'lishi, u yakunlangach esa o'yin natijalari tahlil qilinishi lozim. O'yin orqali o'qitish texnologiyalari ham o'quv-tarbiyaviy jarayonda talabalarning chuqur bilim olishiga keng imkoniyatlar yaratib beradi. Ingliz tilini o'rgatishda talabalarni qiziqtirib o'qitish va bilimlarni to'liq o'zlashtirishlariga erishish zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarning asosiy maqsadlaridan biri hisoblanadi.

Ingliz tilini o'qitish usullaridan yana biri – zamonaviy interaktiv usulidir. Usul mazmuniga ko'ra, darsda yangi grammatik mavzu e'lon qilinib, o'qituvchi uni turli yo'llar, ya'ni doskaga har xil chizmalar chizish, harakatlar bilan ko'rsatish, avvalgi o'tilgan mavzu bilan taqqoslash bilan tushuntirishi, mustahkamlovchi savollar bilan talabalarni fikrlashga jalb etishi lozim. Fonetik mashg'ulotlarda esa, asosan, audiomatndagi qisqa suhbatlar tinglanib, ushbu audiomatndagi suhbatga aynan mos bo'lgan, so'zlari tushirib qoldirilgan qog'ozdagi matn to'ldiriladi. Talabaga berilgan matn bilan audiomatndagi suhbat bir xil bo'ladi. Matn o'ta ziyorlik bilan tinglanib, yangi iboralarni yodda saqlab qolgandagina, talaba shartni muvaffaqiyatli bajarishi mumkin. Bunda tinglab tushunish orqali og'zaki nutq, ko'nikma va malakalar shakllanib boradi. Tinglab tushunish o'qish jarayoni bilan chambarchas bog'liqdir. Tinglovchi o'qigan so'zlarini yaxshi eslab qoladi va

tinglaganida yaxshi tushunadi. Tinglab tushunishni o'rgatishning mazmunini G.V.Rogova uch qismga bo'ladi:

1. Lingvistik qism. Bunga til va nutq materiali kiradi.
2. Psixologik qism. Bu ovozli nutqni tinglash, tushunish malaka va ko'nikmasini hosil qilishdir.
3. Metodik qism. Tinglovchilarga tinglash usullarini o'rgatish hamda tinglab tushunish texnologiyasi orqali qonun-qoida, tamoyillar, metodlar, vositalar orqali o'rgatish amalga oshiriladi.

O'qitish jarayonida tinglab tushunish ustida ishlaganda, kundalik yangiliklar, tili o'rganilayotgan mamlakat xalqlari hayoti, madaniyati, tarixi haqida matnlarning bo'lishi tinglovchilarning qiziqishlarini yanada orttiradi. O'qituvchi tinglab tushunishni o'rgatayotganida, ya'ni tinglovchi notanish mazmundagi nutqni tinglaganida quyidagilarga e'tibor berishi zarur:

1. Ayrim so'zlarni, gaplarni, jummalarni tushunish (fragmenting comprehension).
2. Hamma dalil-fikrlarni to'liq tushunish (comprehension in details).
3. Asosiy dalil-fikrlarni yuzaki tushunish (overall comprehension).
4. Tanqidiy tushunish (critical comprehension).

O'qituvchi eshittirish uchun matn tanlaganida, tinglovchilarning yoshi, bilim darajasi, o'zlashtirishlarini hisobga olishi zarur. Misol uchun, biror notanish matn tanlanadi. Matndagi notanish so'zlar, iboralar matn sarlavhasi doskaga yoziladi. Matn yuzasidan savol-javoblar ham o'tkazilishi mumkin.

Bundan tashqari, tinglovchilarni uy o'qishi jarayonida insho yozishga ham o'rgatish mumkin. Ular insho mavzulari bilan tanishgach, xohlagan mavzuni tanlab uyda insho yozishlari mumkin.

Masalan:

1. Siz yoqtirgan asar qahramoni.
2. Asardagi salbiy va ijobiy obrazlarga xarakteristika bering.

3. Jeyn Eyrning bolalik davri.

4. Asarning asosiy qahramoni haqida fikrmulohazalaringiz va hokazo.

Bunda leksik-grammatik qiyinchiliklar vujudga keladi. Talabalarni o'z fikrlarini bildirishga undash, matn mavzusini yoritishga qisman o'qituvchining o'zi ham yordam berib turishi kerak.

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